

THE ROLE OF WORK ENGAGEMENT IN THE RELATIONSHIP OF ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE AND SELF EFFICACY TO ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR IN HOSPITAL NURSES IN KENDARI CITY; A SOCIAL LEARNING THEORY PERSPECTIVE

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.13811688](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13811688)

Abstract

This study examines the role of work engagement in bridging the influence of organizational justice and self-efficacy on organizational citizenship behavior. The respondents of this study were hospital nurses in Kendari city as many as 413 people. Testing the structural model developed in this study using Analysis of Moment Structure (AMOS) and Statistical Program for Social Science (SPSS) version 22, both of which are statistical tools from IBM. The test results show that work engagement has a significant role in strengthening the relationship of organizational justice and self efficacy to organizational citizenship behavior. This study also found that work engagement can be an effective catalyst for the relationship between self efficacy and organizational citizenship behavior. The findings of this study can contribute to strengthening social learning theory, especially in the context of the causal relationship between organizational justice, self efficacy, work engagement, and organizational citizenship behavior. In addition, this study can contribute to hospital management in Kendari City in implementing and developing human resource management strategies, especially for nurses in hospitals.

Keywords: Organizational Justice, Self Efficacy, Work Engagement, Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

INTRODUCTION

Human resources are the most important asset in an organization, including in hospitals (Kim, Lee, and Lee 2023).. Nurses, as an integral part of the medical team, play a crucial role in providing optimal health services. Nurse management is not only about ensuring the availability of sufficient numbers of nurses, but also about ensuring their quality and job satisfaction (Schug et al. 2022). (Schug et al. 2022). The challenges faced by hospitals in managing nurses include increased workload, the need to maintain work-life balance, and the demand to always provide the best service (Alkorashy and Alana, 2002). (Alkorashy and Alanazi 2023)..

One of the important concepts in human resource management in hospitals is the creation of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). (Liu et al. 2023). This behavior refers to voluntary attitudes shown by employees that go beyond their formal duties, such as helping colleagues, showing initiative, and actively participating in

organizational activities. (Dulahu et al. 2024).. For nurses, organizational citizenship behavior is very important because it can improve the efficiency of hospital operations and the quality of service to patients. Nurses who exhibit organizational citizenship behavior are usually more committed, more proactive, and better able to work together in teams, all of which contribute to a more positive and productive work environment. (Dulahu et al. 2024; Liu et al. 2023)..

To encourage organizational citizenship behavior among nurses, hospitals need to ensure the presence of organizational justice (Shimamura et al. 2021).. When nurses feel they are treated fairly in terms of workload distribution, decision-making processes, and interactions with superiors and co-workers, they are more likely to be motivated to contribute voluntarily and exhibit organizational citizenship behavior (Lönqvist et al. 2022). (Lönqvist et al. 2022).. Conversely, injustice can lower morale and inhibit these positive behaviors. However, some previous studies found that the effect of organizational justice on organizational citizenship behavior is not always consistent. Some studies show a strong positive effect, while others find a weak or even insignificant effect (Alanoğlu and Demir, 2012). (Alanoğlu and Demirtaş 2021; K and Ranjit 2022; I. U. Khan et al. 2023; Rahman and Karim 2022; Williams, Pitre, and Zainuba 2002)..

In addition, self-efficacy is also an important factor in encouraging organizational citizenship behavior. Nurses who have high self-efficacy feel more confident in carrying out their tasks and facing the challenges at hand. (Na-Nan, Kanthong, and Jountrakul 2021; Riyanto 2022).. This confidence allows them to take more initiative, participate in additional activities, and support coworkers. However, like organizational justice, the effect of self-efficacy on organizational citizenship behavior also shows mixed results in research. There are studies that found a significant positive relationship (Na-Nan et al. 2021), while others show less consistent results (Syah and Safrida 2024).

To overcome the inconsistency in the influence of organizational justice and self-efficacy on organizational citizenship behavior, work engagement is presented as a solution variable. Work engagement describes how involved, passionate, and dedicated a nurse is to their work. (Wang et al. 2023). Nurses who are fully engaged in their work usually show high energy, enthusiasm, and deep emotional involvement. (Tran 2023). This engagement often encourages proactive and collaborative behaviors that are hallmarks of organizational citizenship behavior. Work engagement can act as a mediator that strengthens the relationship between organizational justice and self-efficacy with organizational citizenship behavior, by creating a more supportive and motivating work environment. (Simbula, Margheritti, and Avanzi 2023)..

The important role of work engagement lies in its ability to increase nurses' intrinsic motivation and emotional involvement in their work. When nurses feel emotionally engaged and energetic, they are more likely to respond to the justice they feel and the confidence they have by exhibiting behaviors that support organizational goals. (Kim et al. 2023). In other words, work engagement can strengthen the positive effects of organizational justice and self-efficacy on organizational citizenship behavior, thus creating a more harmonious and productive work environment.

This study is examined with the Social Learning Theory analysis knife which is one of its novelty. Social Learning Theory states that individual behavior is learned through

observation and interaction with the surrounding environment. (Bal and Ceyhun 2022).. With this theory, the study will explore how nurses learn and internalize organizational citizenship behavior through observations of coworkers' behavior and interactions with organizational justice systems and job support. (Jin 2022). This approach offers a new perspective on how factors such as organizational justice, self-efficacy, and work engagement can interact and contribute to the formation of organizational citizenship behavior among nurses, providing deeper insights and practical solutions for human resource management in hospitals.

Therefore, this study aims to determine the mediating role of work engagement in organizational justice and self efficacy on organizational citizenship behavior. This research is expected to be useful in the development of nurses, especially in the development of human resources in hospitals. Furthermore, this research is expected to contribute to the development of social learning theory and its application in the field of human resource management, especially in the study of organizational citizenship behavior of hospital nurses in Kendari City. In addition, the originality of this study was also carried out by modifying the research construct indicators.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Social Learning Theory

Social Learning Theory developed by Albert Bandura emphasizes that learning occurs in a social context through observation and imitation of others' behavior. (Jin 2022). According to Bandura, individuals can learn by observing the actions and consequences of others' behavior, which then influence their own behavior. This theory highlights the importance of cognitive processes in learning, such as attention, memory, and motivation (Kruis, Seo, et al., 2012). (Kruis, Seo, and Kim 2020).. Bandura also introduced the concept of self-efficacy, which is a person's belief in their ability to succeed in a particular task, which plays an important role in determining how individuals react to challenges and regulate their behavior (Zeb et al. 2023). (Zeb et al. 2023). This theory has been applied in various contexts, including education, management, clinical psychology, and mass communication, to understand and influence human behavior.

Organizational Justice

Organizational justice is a concept that refers to employee perceptions of justice in the organization, which includes three main components: distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice. (I. U. Khan et al. 2023).. Distributive justice, as described by Adams (1965) through equity theory, focuses on the fairness of employees' perceptions of the distribution of outcomes or rewards based on their inputs. (Ravina-Ripoll et al. 2024).. Procedural justice, proposed by Leventhal (1980), includes the fairness of the processes and procedures used to make decisions, with indicators such as consistency, freedom from bias, and accuracy of information. (Park and Kim 2023). Interactional justice, detailed by Bies and Moag (1986), consists of two subcomponents: interpersonal justice, which involves fairness in treatment and courtesy by superiors, and informational justice, which deals with the honesty and completeness of information provided to employees. (Song et al. 2023). Lambert et al. (2021) and Lambert et al. (2023) also developed organizational justice measurement tools as follows: fair promotion opportunities, recognition of hard work, fair

performance appraisal procedures, fair supervisor attitudes, performance appraisals that are appropriate, and competency-based rewards.

Self Efficacy

The concept of self-efficacy, developed by Albert Bandura, refers to an individual's belief in his or her ability to execute the actions required to achieve a particular goal. (Ferreira et al. 2022).. An individual's level of self-efficacy is closely related to goal achievement, self-adjustment, and psychological well-being, and has a significant impact on motivation, performance, and mental resilience. The concept of self-efficacy is important in the context of education, self-development, and human resource management, as it influences individual behavior in achieving success and increasing productivity. (Vachova, Sedlakova, and Kvintova 2023; Yang, Wu, and Li 2023).. Self-efficacy indicators proposed by experts include Maddux (1995) who emphasizes the level of individual confidence in overcoming challenges, Bandura (1994) who measures self-efficacy with perceptions of self-control ability in dealing with difficult situations, Zimmerman (2000) who suggests belief in the ability to overcome obstacles in achieving goals, and Schwarzer & Jerusalem (1995) who offer indicators of the level of optimism and perseverance in the face of obstacles. (Suzuki et al. 2023; Zhang 2022).. In addition, Bandura's (1994) view modified by Tang (2021) In addition, Bandura's (1994) view, modified by Tang (2021), states that self-efficacy can be measured by indicators: confident of being able to complete work, confident that you can motivate yourself to complete work, confident that you can try hard to complete work, confident that you can face obstacles at work, and confident that you can complete work in various situations.

Work Engagement

Work engagement refers to the high level of emotional, cognitive, and behavioral involvement of employees in their work. (Johnson 2022). Various studies have shown that work engagement has a positive correlation with productivity, performance, job satisfaction, and employee retention, and is a strong predictor of a variety of desirable organizational outcomes. (Anshori et al. 2023; Prieto-Díeza et al. 2022).. In the context of human resource management, understanding and facilitating work engagement is key to improving employee performance and well-being, as well as creating a positive and productive work environment. (Lee, Sim, and Tuckey 2024).. The indicators of work engagement described by experts include Schaufeli & Bakker (2004) measure work engagement through vigor, dedication, and absorption. (Lipscomb et al. 2022; Sheikh et al. 2019).. Saks (2006) added a high level of focus and concentration on work tasks, while Bakker & Demerouti (2008) emphasized feelings of satisfaction and pride in the results achieved. (Kulikowski 2023). Kahn (1990) mentions that work engagement is also characterized by feelings of deep involvement with organizational goals and values, while Salanova et al. (2005) added that there is a sense of responsibility and commitment to work. (Szilvassy and Širok 2022).. Other than that, Tawil et al., (2023) presents 2 additional indicators in the form of focus and going the extra mile as a reflection of the work engagement construct.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) refers to voluntary behavior that is not listed in the formal role of employees, but makes a positive contribution to organizational performance and effectiveness. (Khalilzadeh and Ghesmati 2024).. Understanding and facilitating organizational citizenship behavior is important for human resource

management in creating a collaborative, productive, and long-term goal-oriented work culture for the organization. (Arquimino Ramos and Lena Ellitan 2023; Lin, Xie, and Li 2023).. There are various indicators of organizational citizenship behavior proposed by experts including; Podsakoff (1990) mentions helping fellow employees, then Organ (1988) states that he has loyalty to the organization and obedience to organizational rules and policies. Organ & Ryan (1995) added supporting superiors and colleagues, while Bolino & Turnley (2005) emphasized proactive initiatives in improving organizational processes and performance. In addition, Smith et al. (1983) stated that organizational citizenship behavior includes behaviors that maintain and improve the image of the organization. (Arquimino Ramos and Lena Ellitan 2023; Donkor, Segbenya, and Ofosuhene 2023; Syah and Safrida 2024).. In addition, there is a renewal of Organ's organizational citizenship behavior indicator (1996) by El-Sayed Ghonem (2023), Johansson and Hart (2023), and Langdon, Fletcher, and Carr (2024). including; altruism, conscientiousness, civic virtue, sportsmanship, and courtesy.

Organizational Justice and Work Engagement

Organizational justice in various studies has consistently been found to have a positive correlation with employee work engagement (Deressa et al. 2022; I. U. Khan et al. 2023).. Previous studies have shown that when employees feel they are treated fairly regarding the distribution of resources, procedures used to make decisions, and interpersonal interactions, they tend to show higher work engagement. (Mubashar et al. 2022).. These feelings of fairness increase employees' trust in the organization, encourage them to invest more in their tasks, and increase emotional commitment and intrinsic motivation. Conversely, perceptions of unfairness can reduce work engagement, leading to negative attitudes such as emotional exhaustion and intentions to leave the organization. (Hermanto and Srimulyani 2022; Mubashar et al. 2022; Suharto et al. 2022).. Ensuring fairness in various aspects of organizational operations is not only important for employee well-being but also for improving overall performance and productivity. (Ravina-Ripoll et al. 2024).. Based on this description, the following research hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Organizational justice has a significant positive effect on work engagement.

Self Efficacy and Work Engagement

Previous research shows that employees with high self-efficacy will have higher work engagement because they feel more confident in facing job challenges and are better able to overcome obstacles that may arise. (Heng and Chu 2023). These beliefs increase intrinsic motivation, perseverance, and initiative at work, which in turn encourages deeper and more sustained engagement in their tasks. (Salhieh and Al-Abdallat 2022; Zhang 2022).. In addition, high self-efficacy is also associated with feeling greater control over their work, which increases job satisfaction and commitment to the organization (Heng and Chu 2023). (Heng and Chu 2023). In contrast, employees with low self-efficacy tend to feel less capable and less motivated, which can reduce work engagement levels and negatively impact overall performance (Robalino Guerra and Chu 2023). (Robalino Guerra and Musso 2022). Improving self-efficacy through training and professional development can be an effective strategy to increase work engagement in the workplace. Based on this explanation, the following research hypothesis is proposed:

H2: Self efficacy has a significant positive effect on work engagement.

Organizational Justice and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Previous studies on organizational justice, which includes distributive, procedural, and interactional justice, were found to have a positive influence on organizational citizenship behavior, which is employee behavior that goes beyond formal duties and supports the overall functioning of the organization (Nguyen and Le 2023). (Nguyen and Le 2023). Research results show that when employees feel they are treated fairly in resource distribution, decision-making procedures, and interpersonal interactions, they are more likely to exhibit altruistic behavior, help colleagues, and show high loyalty and initiative. (Das and Mohanty 2023; Waskito et al. 2023).. This sense of fairness increases employees' trust and commitment to the organization, which motivates them to contribute beyond formal job responsibilities (Abbasi et al. 2022). (Abbasi et al. 2022; Nguyen and Le 2023).. Conversely, perceptions of injustice can reduce motivation to engage in organizational citizenship behavior and even encourage counterproductive behaviors (Adugna et al. 2022).. Based on this explanation, the following research hypothesis is proposed:

H3: Organizational justice has a significant positive effect on organizational citizenship behavior.

Self Efficacy and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Various studies suggest that self-efficacy, which is an individual's belief in their ability to succeed in a particular task, significantly influences organizational citizenship behavior, which includes employee behaviors that go beyond their formal duties and support organizational effectiveness. (Yada et al. 2022). Previous research has also shown that employees with high levels of self-efficacy are more likely to engage in organizational citizenship behavior because they have strong confidence to take initiative, help colleagues, and contribute positively to their work environment. (Broccia, Dias, and Pereira 2022).. These beliefs encourage proactive behavior, extra responsibility, and commitment to the organization, which are all key elements of organizational citizenship behavior. (H. S. ud din Khan et al. 2023).. In addition, high self-efficacy also increases employees' ability to face challenges and overcome obstacles, which in turn strengthens their motivation to support colleagues and contribute to organizational goals. (Hermanto, Srimulyani, and Pitoyo 2024).. In contrast, employees with low self-efficacy feel less able to engage in organizational citizenship behavior, which can have a negative impact on team dynamics and organizational performance. (Langdon et al. 2024). Based on this description, the following research hypothesis is proposed:

H4: Self efficacy has a significant positive effect on organizational citizenship behavior.

Work Engagement and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Work engagement, which reflects an employee's level of involvement, enthusiasm, and commitment to his or her job, has been found to consistently have a positive correlation with organizational citizenship behavior. (Zhou, Gul, and Tufail 2022).. Employees who have high levels of work engagement tend to exhibit greater organizational citizenship behaviors, such as helping colleagues, taking initiative, and supporting organizational goals beyond their formal duties. This is because engaged employees feel more motivated and connected to the organization, making them more willing to contribute voluntarily for the collective good. (Alkorashy and Alanazi 2023). In addition, work engagement increases employees' energy and resilience, which

enables them to participate in proactive and supportive behaviors. (Kim et al. 2023). Thus, increasing work engagement can be an effective strategy to encourage organizational citizenship behavior and improve overall organizational performance. (Neuber et al. 2022; Yao et al. 2022).. Based on this description, the following research hypothesis is proposed:

H5: Work engagement has a significant positive effect on organizational citizenship behavior.

Organizational Justice, Work Engagement, and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Previous research shows that organizational justice has a direct effect on increasing organizational citizenship behavior. (K and Ranjit 2022; Nguyen and Le 2023; Waskito et al. 2023). However, this effect can be strengthened through work engagement (Kim et al. 2023). Other studies show that employees' perceptions of organizational justice can increase their level of work engagement, which includes a sense of enthusiasm, commitment, and involvement with their work (Liu et al. 2023). (Liu et al. 2023). Employees who feel they are treated fairly tend to be more engaged in their work, as well as motivating them to go beyond formal tasks and exhibit organizational citizenship behaviors, such as helping colleagues and actively participating in organizational activities. (Chinyamurindi, Mathibe, and Marange 2023).. In other words, work engagement acts as a mediator that explains how and why organizational justice can encourage employees to behave proactively. (Kim 2023). Therefore, increasing the perception of justice in the workplace will be able to increase work engagement so that it has a significant impact on increasing organizational citizenship behavior. Based on this description, the following research hypothesis is proposed:

H6: Organizational justice has a significant positive effect on organizational citizenship behavior through the mediation of work engagement.

Self Efficacy, Work Engagement, and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Several previous studies have shown that self-efficacy positively affects organizational citizenship behavior. (Syah and Safrida 2024). However, this influence can be strengthened through work engagement (Uppathampracha and Liu 2022).. Other studies show that high self-efficacy increases work engagement, where employees feel more motivated, energized, and engaged in their work. Employees who are confident in their abilities tend to be more engaged in their tasks, and this engagement motivates them to contribute more than expected, such as helping coworkers and showing high initiative (Heng and Chu 2023). (Heng and Chu 2023). Thus, work engagement acts as a mediator that explains how and why self-efficacy can encourage employees to show organizational citizenship behavior. (Meria et al. 2022). Good self-efficacy will be able to encourage increased work engagement so that it has an impact on increasing organizational citizenship behavior. Based on this description, the following research hypothesis is proposed:

H7: Self efficacy has a significant positive effect on organizational citizenship behavior through the mediation of work engagement.

The research model that describes the relationship between constructs and each indicator can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research Model

METHODS

The population in this study were all nurses totaling 1487 people spread across 13 hospitals in Kendari City. In order for the number of samples to be a representation of the population, the sample determination in each hospital uses a proportional random sampling method of 413 people. The respondents in this study were hospital nurses in Kendari City.

The research data analysis was carried out using the structural equation model (SEM) technique with the help of AMOS 22 software. (Blunch 2012). The reasons for choosing the SEM technique for this multivariate analysis include: First, SEM is a multivariate analysis technique that can test and display the weight and meaning of indicators simultaneously while testing the relationship and causal influence in the model. Second, the SEM technique has high flexibility in model adjustment, allowing variables to play multiple roles as independent and dependent or mediating variables simultaneously. Third, SEM techniques allow mediation and moderation analysis to be conducted in an integrated manner in one testing process. Fourth, SEM allows the development of competing models to find the model that best fits the sample data. Fifth, SEM allows practical and logical testing of mediation hypotheses to confirm the existence of partial or full mediation. Sixth, with SEM, researchers can easily compare models between sample groups or with competing models, making it faster to justify the most appropriate model supported by sample data. (Blunch 2012; Hair and Sarstedt 2019).

RESULTS

Model testing in this study aims to observe the overall impact of all exogenous variables on endogenous variables. In addition, the model test can also be used to determine whether the model built is statistically significant or not. The original parameters of model testing are the degree of the chi-square test and the level of significance achieved (Hair and Sarstedt 2019). Since these measures are difficult to achieve, experts then developed indices that can represent a good model (Blunch 2012; Henseler 2012). The following figure presents the results of model testing with the achievement of model fit in this study.

Through Figure 2 above, it is known that the results of the model test run show good index fulfillment and are above the specified *cut of value*, so the model is declared fit.

Table 3: Achievement of Model Fit Index

Goodness of Fit Index	Cut of Value	Results	Description
Chi-square	It is expected that the value is small	174.186	Good
Significance Probability	≥ 0.05	0.000	Good
CMIN/DF	≤ 2.00	2.074	Good
RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0.051	Good
GFI	≥ 0.90	0.947	Good
AGFI	≥ 0.90	0.924	Good
TLI	≥ 0.95	0.989	Good
CFI	≥ 0.95	0.991	Good

The final results of the full SEM test displayed in table 3 show that the model is well confirmed and meet the goodness of fit criteria in accordance with the required rule of thumb. This means that the model can be empirically tested and fits the data used in this study. In addition, the developed model is the most logical model to improve nurses' OCB. Observations on the covariance residuals of the sample data were also made. The limit used in the standardized residual covariances matrix is ± 2.58 at the 5% significance level. The results of the analysis with AMOS software showed that

there were no residual values that exceeded ± 2.58 . (Tabanick and Fidell 2003).. Therefore, this model qualifies as a good model. Thus, regression hypothesis testing can proceed.

This study used 3 stages of hypothesis testing in the data processing process to ensure that each data was carefully processed according to its own purpose. The initial stage was confirmatory factor analysis to identify all the variables used in the study (Blunch 2012). (Blunch 2012). The next stage is to conduct simultaneous testing of all hypotheses developed in this structural model, with the aim of ensuring that each hypothesis has been effectively tested through full structural model testing (Byrne 2016). (Byrne 2016). The final stage is to test the mediation relationships that have been developed in this study for variables that have been predetermined as mediating variables (Marcoulides, Foldnes, Byrne 2016). (Marcoulides, Foldnes, and Grønneberg 2020).. The results of the causality hypothesis test run can be seen in the following table;

Table 4: Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis	Estimate	S.E.	C.R	P	Conclusion
H1: Organizational justice → work engagement	0.388	0,040	9.652	***	Accepted
H2: Self-efficacy → work engagement	0.284	0.043	6.626	***	Accepted
H3: Organizational justice → OCB	0.246	0.050	4.890	***	Accepted
H4: Self-efficacy → OCB	0.037	0.052	0.710	0.478	Rejected
H5: Work engagement → OCB	0.648	0.064	10.074	***	Accepted

Hypothesis testing above uses the T test criterion which in SEM testing is referred to as the Critical Ratio (CR). A statistical measure of CR exceeding a value > 1.96 indicates a good level of significance for H1, H2, H3, and H5, while H4 is rejected with a value of $p = 0.478 (> 0.05)$. This study also developed a mediating variable in the form of work engagement which is a solution to the research gap of this research problem. The test results are shown in the following table.

Table 5: Mediation Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis	Estimate	S.E	C.R.	P	Conclusion
H6: Organizational justice → work engagement → OCB	0.251	0.044	5.678	***	Accepted
H7: Self-efficacy → work engagement → OCB	0.161	0.043	3.753	***	Accepted

From table 5, it is known that based on the results of the mediation test conducted, the CR value > 1.96 with significance < 0.05 for OJ → WE → OCB and SE → WE → OCB, thus the mediating variable can show its mediating role in all existing relationships so that H6 and H7 are declared accepted.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study show that organizational justice and self-efficacy affect work engagement. From a social learning theory perspective, this can be understood through the process of observation and modeling. When nurses feel that they are treated fairly in the organization, they observe and model this positive behavior, which increases their feelings of engagement at work. In addition, when nurses have high confidence in their own abilities, there is a tendency to observe and model behaviors that demonstrate competence and success, which also increases their engagement. In this context, work engagement is a result of social learning where perceptions of

fairness and strong self-beliefs increase nurses' motivation and commitment to their work. This finding is in line with the study results from Deressa et al. (2022), I. U. Khan et al. (2023), Mubashar et al. (2022), Heng and Chu (2023), Salhieh and Al-Abdallat (2022), and Zhang (2022). This study also found that organizational justice has a significant positive effect on organizational citizenship behavior which supports the results of the study from Nguyen and Le (2023), Das and Mohanty (2023), and Waskito et al. (2023). Meanwhile, self-efficacy shows the opposite result, namely that it has no effect on organizational citizenship behavior as the results of the study from Alshaikh and Bond (2020), Gashi Tresi and Mihelič (2020), and Mahipalan, Sheena, and Muhammed (2019).. These results provide some significance, in that when nurses feel that they are treated fairly, they are more likely to perform voluntary actions that help the hospital and their coworkers, or actively participate in hospital activities. On the other hand, while self-efficacy is important in determining how one performs individual tasks, this belief is not sufficient to drive more complex behaviors such as organizational citizenship behavior. From a social learning theory perspective, this result can be explained through the influence of social models in organizations.

When nurses observe that the hospital applies justice consistently, they will imitate the fair behavior, which in turn increases their tendency to engage in organizational citizenship behavior. Organizational justice serves as a behavioral model that nurses internalize, creates a supportive work environment, and motivates positive behaviors that go beyond formal duties. Behaviors such as self-efficacy, on the other hand, tend to be influenced by motivational and emotional factors rooted in perceptions of the work environment and interpersonal relationships, rather than simply an individual's belief in his or her own abilities. Self-efficacy is more relevant for individual task performance than for voluntary and contextual behaviors. Work engagement in this study serves as an important factor that reinforces the process of observation and internalization of positive behaviors in the work environment. When nurses are psychologically and emotionally committed to their work, receptive behaviors emerge as a result of observations from their colleagues and superiors. This increases their tendency to mimic fair behavior and trust their own abilities. Thus, work engagement not only motivates nurses to imitate positive behaviors, but also strengthens the impact of organizational justice and self-efficacy on organizational citizenship behavior as reported by Zhou, Gul, and Tufail (2022), Alkorashy and Alanazi (2023), Kim et al. (2023), Neuber et al. (2022), Yao et al. (2022), Bonaiuto et al. (2022), and Kim (2023).

The above findings further confirm that work engagement acts as an important link that converts nurses' positive perceptions into beneficial actions. Nurses who feel treated fairly and have high confidence in their abilities tend to be more engaged at work. This engagement then motivates them to exhibit positive behaviors such as helping colleagues and taking more initiative, although the direct effect of self-efficacy on organizational citizenship behavior is not significant in the absence of work engagement. This means that work engagement strengthens the impact of organizational justice and self-efficacy, thus creating a work environment that is more supportive of positive behaviors such as organizational citizenship behavior. These findings emphasize the importance of fair management practices and self-development programs to increase work engagement. By improving work engagement, hospitals can maximize nurses' potential to contribute positively, transforming perceptions and beliefs into concrete actions that benefit the hospital.

Theoretical Implications

The findings of this study can contribute to the development of social learning theory and the concept of work engagement as the best catalyst that strengthens the relationship of organizational justice and self-efficacy to organizational citizenship behavior. Furthermore, the findings of this study also provide theoretical contributions regarding the role of work engagement as an important factor that strengthens the process of observation and internalization of positive behavior in the work environment, in addition to being a motivational tool for creating organizational citizenship behavior.

Managerial Implications

The findings of this study can provide practical contributions to hospital management in Kendari City in the form of strategies for creating organizational citizenship behavior for nurses, strengthening work engagement, increasing organizational justice, and improving self-efficacy so as to develop positive behaviors in order to provide the best service for hospital consumers. The findings of this study also serve as a reference for hospital management in Kendari City in formulating nurse development strategies and making managerial decisions.

CONCLUSION

This study focuses on examining the mediating role of work engagement in strengthening the causal relationship between organizational justice and self-efficacy on organizational citizenship behavior from the perspective of social learning theory. This study also developed indicators of work engagement as a solution variable. The results of this study conclude that work engagement is empirically proven to strengthen the influence of organizational justice and self efficacy on organizational citizenship behavior in hospital nurses in Kendari City through social learning mechanisms.

Limitation and Future Research

This research model is limited to hospital nurses in Kendari City with a limited number of respondents. Therefore, it is recommended that future research expand the coverage area and test the model in different organizations, such as education, finance, and services. In addition, this study only uses exogenous variables in the form of organizational justice and self-efficacy and utilizes work engagement as a mediating variable. In future research, it is recommended to test other variables that can strengthen the mediating role of work engagement on organizational citizenship behavior, such as; perceived organizational support, leadership quality, organizational climate, and reward system.

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